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Title: Participatory cinema and migration

Abstract:

Based on a participatory methodological approach that triangulates Responsible Research and Innovation (Deblonde, 2015), action-research (Stringer, 2013) and socio-ecological models (Partelow, 2016), our research project on refugees has worked in action-research units located in 7 countries that make up the RAISD European Project consortium (Finland, Italy, Turkey, Jordan, Hungary, Spain, and Lebanon). One of the most relevant results of the project has been the development of the documentary “Espejismos”.

These units are permanent action-research laboratories in which all research and innovation actions have been co-designed with the rest of the involved social actors: NGO representatives, policy makers, researchers, businesses, refugees and asylum seekers, and other members of civil society related to this issue. In the case of Spain, where representatives from all these areas regularly participate, around twenty people have collaborated on the documentary and the transmedia webdoc, mainly refugees and asylum seekers, specialized researchers, and NGOs.

In this communication we present the most outstanding results of this participatory method in which the process of creation and production of the documentary has been supported, as well as the main findings regarding the challenges and synergies that have emerged throughout the process.

References:

Deblonde, M. (2015). Responsible research and innovation: Building knowledge arenas for glocal sustainability research. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 2(1), 20-38.

Partelow, S. (2016). Coevolving Ostrom’s social–ecological systems (SES) framework and sustainability science: four key co-benefits. *Sustainability Science*, 11(3), 399-410.

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